

INVESTIGATION BLOW-UP SOLUTION OF NON-DIVERGENT NONLINEAR PARABOLIC SYSTEM EQUATIONS DESCRIBING THE PROCESSES OF COMBUSTION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15612360>

Currently, mathematical models of diffusion processes characterized by non-divergent systems of parabolic equations are being widely studied in the worldwide. Therefore, the determination of new qualitative properties of nonlinear models with blow-up mode is one of the most relevant scientific studies. The asymptotic behavior of positive solutions of the Cauchy problem for nonlinear equations was studied in [1]. Global and blow-up solutions to the Cauchy problem are analyzed in [2-3].

In this work, we consider the Cauchy problem for a system of nonlinear parabolic equations not in divergence form, in the domain $Q = \{(t, x) : t > 0, x \in R\}$.

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = u^{\alpha_1} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (u^{m-1} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x}) - v^{\beta_1} \\ \frac{\partial v}{\partial t} = v^{\alpha_2} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (v^{m-1} \frac{\partial v}{\partial x}) - u^{\beta_2} \end{cases}$$

and initial conditions
$$\begin{cases} u(0, x) = u_0(x) \geq 0 \\ v(0, x) = v_0(x) \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

where $\beta_1 > 0, \beta_2 > 0, \beta_1 \beta_2 < 1, \alpha_1 < 1, \alpha_2 < 1$ - numerical parameters.

The system of equations (1) has been studied by several authors for different values and cases of the parameter p (see, for example, [1–3] and the references therein). In this work, the qualitative properties of the solution to problem (1)–(2), depending on the values of the numerical parameters and the initial data, are considered. First, a self-similar solution is found, asymptotic estimates are obtained, and several theorems are presented and proved based on these estimates. Then, using the theoretical results, numerical solutions are computed and a graphical visualization of the model is constructed.

Theorem. If $n_1(\alpha_1 + m - 1) < 1, n_2(\alpha_2 + m - 1) < 1$ and $\alpha_1 < 1, \alpha_2 < 1$ then, the problem (1)–(2) has a generalized solution with estimate:

$$u_+(t, x) = B \cdot \bar{u}(t) \cdot \left(a - A_1 x^2 (T - t) \right)^{\frac{-n_1(\alpha_1 + m - 1) + 1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{\alpha_1 + m - 1}}, v_+(t, x) = C \cdot \bar{v}(t) \cdot \left(a - A_2 x^2 (T - t) \right)^{\frac{-n_2(\alpha_2 + m - 1) + 1}{2}}^{\frac{1}{\alpha_2 + m - 1}}$$

where $\bar{u}(t), \bar{v}(t), \xi$ are the functions defined above.

Obtaining estimates is also useful when an exact solution cannot be found. The upper solution obtained provides preliminary information about the exact solution.

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